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Evaluation Framework

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3 List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DIPL	Dilemma Game from the project partner Serious Games Interactive
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
EB	Editorial Board
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PLAYMOB	Online game from project partner Playmob
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

4 Executive Summary

The overall objective of GREAT is using game-based methods for the political and social engagement of citizens regarding the climate crisis, aiming to address current policy issues and closing the gap between citizens and policymakers. This document provides the basis for the evaluation and impact assessment performed during the course of the project. It discusses theoretical concepts that have been combined to define an evaluation framework specifically designed for GREAT. The framework builds on public engagement and participation concepts, such as Citizen Science, next to gamified approaches, all with a special view on Climate Change as the core topic of concern in GREAT.

We focus our impact assessment on four dimensions following a logic model approach and for each of these dimensions we define a set of indicators and methods on data gathering:

- Scientific dimension
- Individual actors' dimension
- Economic dimension
- Societal dimension

The logic models for each of these dimensions allows us to present logical relationships between the project's inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts. For defining appropriate indicators for each of the dimension we relate them back to the theoretical concepts that we discuss in this document and match them with the two distinct game-based interventions (DIBL and Playmob). The data collection instruments that we plan to apply across the GREAT case studies include qualitative and quantitative measures, such as interviews and questionnaires.

Within the constraints of the project time frame, we will most probably only be able to collect data at output and outcomes level. However, we will also try to identify indications of possible impact, which holds a long-term perspective. The evaluation and impact assessment approach presented in this document offers a comprehensive and modular approach, which will be tailored to the specific case studies in the course of the GREAT project.

5 Introduction

This deliverable describes the overall evaluation framework for the GREAT project and its development for evaluating and interpreting the data collected during GREAT, drawing from previous work on citizen participation and engagement as well as game-based approaches. As such, this deliverable is embedded within the GREAT project's WP5, the goal of which is to assess the project, study the social use and impact of the games developed within GREAT, and to provide evidence for the effectiveness of game-based participatory processes.

The main aim of the evaluation framework in GREAT is to bring evidence of the impact that the project's activities have on the involved actors, such as participants in our case studies (co-researchers, citizen scientists, players, subject experts, etc.), scientists, industrial partners, as well as on their wider socio-cultural contexts. Additionally, the formative evaluation aims at the assessment of activities and instruments that are applied throughout the research cycle of each case study, such as ease of use and perceived usefulness of the involvement activities, offered materials, developed prototypes, and the research process as a whole. This input will iteratively shape our interaction activities, the materials and implementations, trying to detect the non-conformances that may occur during the citizen science research process as well as drivers for engagement and usage.

The deliverable is structured along the following chapters:

- Presentation of theoretical approach and key concepts relevant for GREAT
 - Public engagement with climate change
 - Games and gamification for climate change
 - Evaluation and impact assessment in citizen science
- Evaluation and impact assessment methodology including logic models along four dimensions (scientific, individual actors, economic, societal), measure and indicators that relate back to the theoretical concepts.
- Detailed evaluation instruments in the Appendix

This document is the basis for the further evaluation and impact assessment activities of the GREAT project.

6 Theoretical Approach and Key Concepts

The objective of GREAT is using game-based methods for the political and social engagement of citizens regarding the climate crisis, aiming to address current policy issues and closing the gap between citizens and policymakers. The following sections embed the project and its activities into current theoretical and empirical literature by discussing key concepts used throughout this deliverable before outlining the evaluation and impact assessment of GREAT.

6.1 Public Engagement with Climate Change

Previous research has conceptualised public engagement with climate change from two main perspectives (Kumpu, 2022). On one hand, public engagement is rooted in political and participatory research, where it describes a process of involving citizens in policy, science, or in community decision-making. On the other hand, public engagement is a concept used in psychology whereby engagement is an individual's cognitive, affective, and behavioural connection with climate change (Lorenzoni et al., 2007). This perspective sees engagement as an individual outcome that may be increased with methods such as targeted communication or interventions. Both perspectives are relevant for the GREAT project and will jointly inform the evaluation activities.

6.1.1 Public engagement processes

Public engagement as a process means facilitating the political participation of citizens to support the exchange of information between citizens and policy representatives (Huitema et al., 2010; Rowe et al., 2008). The overall aim of this process usually is to improve the quality, legitimacy, and transparency of policy decisions, which in turn should increase citizens' support for these policies in the long-term. As such, public engagement is embedded in a political or social system and used as a tool for collective decision-making (Kumpu, 2022). Reed et al. (2018) provide a framework to classify different engagement processes by integrating the **level of agency** of involved stakeholders with the **mode of engagement**, resulting in four main types of engagement. In this framework, engagement is characterised based on who initiates and takes responsibility for the process and to which extent citizens can contribute to developing and making decisions. The first type is top-down **communication or consultation**, whereby an organisation with decision-making power initiates and leads the engagement process and communicates or consults with citizens, yet without involving them in decision-making. Second, in top-down **deliberation or co-production**, an organisation with decision-making power initiates or leads the engagement process and involves citizens to actively contribute to developing decisions. Third, in bottom-up communication or

consultation, the engagement process is initiated by members of the public to affect decisions already made by communicating their opinions to decision-making bodies. Lastly, there is bottom-up deliberation or co-production, whereby members of the public initiate an engagement process to debate and develop decisions together with the organisations in power. As Reed et al. (2018) point out, many cases of engagement processes might fall in-between these four main categories.

Engagement scholars have noted a lack of empirical evidence to support the benefits of public engagement processes, as they are rarely evaluated (Ianniello et al., 2019; Rowe et al., 2008; Whitmarsh et al., 2013). Those studies which evaluated a public engagement process or activity actually provide support for the claim that those actors involved benefit from their engagement, while it is difficult to assess whether engagement processes improve the quality of a given policy (Burton & Mustelin, 2013). For instance, participation in engagement activities on climate change can improve citizens' factual and technical knowledge of the issue and increase trust and understanding towards other citizens, whereas policymakers benefit from the diversity of perspectives provided and learn what the public thinks, thereby improving their future communication and decision-making (Huitema et al., 2010; Wells et al., 2021). However, the benefits of public engagement processes are limited if they only reach the small portion of citizens already actively participating in politics rather than involving the general public or underrepresented groups, cannot convey topical information accurately, or are characterised by power imbalances (Huitema et al., 2010; Ianniello et al., 2019; Loh, 2019; Rowe et al., 2008; Wells et al., 2021). Policymakers might also undermine the benefits of public engagement if they do not take citizens' suggestions seriously and are reluctant to allow citizens to influence their decision-making. A main problem with public engagement activities is that they are resource-intensive while participants might perceive them as boring, lacking transparency, or too one-sided to benefit them. Following these limitations, researchers such as Whitmarsh et al. (2013) have noted a lack of engagement approaches for overcoming these different barriers and effectively engaging citizens.

Different evaluation frameworks have been proposed and tested to systematically assess engagement processes along pre-defined criteria, which represent optimal characteristics of the engagement process (rather than its influence on citizens' outcomes). For instance, Rowe et al., (2008) propose a framework consisting of acceptance criteria – did participants perceive the activity as representative, independent and unbiased, transparent, and were they involved early enough to influence decisions – and process criteria, relating to the accessibility of necessary resources to fulfil the activity, a clear definition of the task as well as of the decision-making involved in the activity, and whether it is cost effective. However, these criteria are strongly related to engagement processes

and agenda-setting initiated top-down by decision-making bodies. In contrast, GREAT will most likely also involve civil society organisations or citizens in preparing the game-based tools working as tools for public engagement. Schroeter et al. (2016) provide a framework more focussed on the interactions between participants and distinguish between three main characteristics of engagement processes. Firstly, public engagement processes should be **inclusive** and represent all stakeholders. To be inclusive, the engagement process should provide an inclusive platform for communicating and negotiating opinions, providing equal opportunities for every participant to participate and contribute. Secondly, engagement processes should emphasise **information exchange and learning** between all participants. To achieve this, an exchange of different types of knowledge and perspectives, access to a common pool of information for all participations, transparency of participants' opinions and reasoning, and a common understanding of the purpose and steps of the engagement process are necessary. The third characteristic refers to the process' **influence on political decisions** and describes the relationship between participants' inputs and the decisions which are eventually taken. More specifically, the participants involved should feel like their opinions were heard, their participation will influence the decision, and that their efforts resulted in a satisfactory outcome. For the purpose of GREAT, we consider these three dimensions as more appropriate to assess participants' experience of participating in the game-based tools.

To summarise, public engagement can be understood on the personal level, describing how an individual deals with climate change – thinks, feels, and acts about climate change – which can be promoted or facilitated. Public engagement can also be understood as a process of involving citizens in climate decision-making, aiming for benefits for both the actors involved and the product of this process. Current opinion surveys suggest that there is still a lot of room for improving engagement and overcoming its individual and structural barriers: though most Europeans recognise climate change as one of the most serious global issues, many have not taken action against climate change and consider their government to be responsible, yet are unsatisfied with their government's performance (European Commission. Directorate General for Climate Action., 2021). Thus, there is a need to improve both the process of engagement to improve support and quality of climate policy as well as the level of personal climate change engagement, equipping citizens with the knowledge, awareness, and readiness to support a sustainable future. The GREAT project aims to promote this goal and address the existing barriers using game-based approaches to improve engagement processes and outcomes.

6.1.2 Personal climate change engagement

Climate change engagement as an individual outcome describes how the individual **thinks, feels, and acts about climate change** (Kumpu, 2022; Lorenzoni et al., 2007). Climate change engagement is a multi-dimensional concept, comprising aspects such as knowledge and understanding of climate science (**cognitive** dimension), climate change awareness, concern, or risk perceptions (**affective** dimension), and behaviours to mitigate climate change, such as sustainable consumption or collective action (**behavioural** dimension). These three dimensions are interconnected in a complex way; for instance, a person who is highly aware of climate change and has a good understanding of climate science does not necessarily perform behaviours for mitigating climate change to the same extent (Chaplin & Wyton, 2014; Redondo & Puelles, 2017). Interventions and measures to promote personal climate change engagement usually focus on emphasising its **local** impacts and how the individual can be personally affected by these impacts, emphasising the social norm that society and the people important to an individual value engaging with climate change, or making the science behind climate change more comprehensible, for instance with visualisations (Van Der Linden et al., 2015; Wibeck, 2014). In turn, a person might not engage with climate change cognitively, affectively or behaviourally if they think they cannot understand climate change as it's too complex and technical, if they feel like they, as an individual, lack the agency to effectively tackle climate change, if they perceive that no one else, neither political actors nor other citizens, tackle climate change, or if they are not supported by the appropriate infrastructure or systems in addressing climate change (Lorenzoni et al., 2007; Van Der Linden et al., 2015; Wibeck, 2014).

The three dimensions of climate change engagement can be broken down into more specific concepts to assess and measure them. The following table (Table 1) provides an overview of the concepts we propose for assessing the GREAT activities and informing the participant evaluation (see section 7.1.1) based on current research. By providing a comprehensive overview of relevant concepts, we enable each case study to select those concepts applicable to their specific activities.

Engagement Dimension	Concept	Description and Relevant Research
Affective climate change engagement	Risk perception	Risk perception describes the extent to which a person feels that climate change poses a threat or is concerned about its impacts (van der Linden, 2015, 2017). Thus, it constitutes a subjective perception of risk rather than capturing objectively existing risks and threats. Risk perception is often distinguished into personal perception – whether the person themselves will experience personal impacts of climate change – and societal risk perceptions, covering whether climate change is a serious issue for other people, including family and friends, their community, or society at large. Risk perception is a strong factor motivating people to act, increasing support for climate policies as well as reports of climate activism and pro-environmental behaviour (Ballew et al., 2019; Goldberg et al., 2021; Haugestad et al., 2021; Lubell et al., 2007; Mayer et al., 2017; Smith & Mayer, 2018).
	Political trust	Trust towards a political institution or political actor implies that the individual does not feel the need to monitor the institution’s behaviour or worry about it, but rather trusts the institution to assess situations and make the right decisions (Levi & Stoker, 2000). This can include political institutions or individual actors, including the national or regional government, parliament, legal system, or politicians. Political trust is a main enabler for climate policy support: those individuals who are highly concerned about climate change are only more likely to support climate policies if they also trust their political institutions and public officials (Cologna & Siegrist, 2020; Fairbrother, 2019; Fairbrother et al., 2019; Rhodes et al., 2017).
	Social trust	Social trust in turn describes an individual’s trust relationship with their social groups, community, or society at large (Smith & Mayer, 2018). Individuals with higher social trust are also more likely to take action against climate change, support climate policies, and contribute to community-based measures against climate change (Cologna & Siegrist, 2020; Gür, 2020; Irwin, 2020; Smith & Mayer, 2018).
	Climate Emotions	Emotional responses to climate change can be defined as affective states that are associated with specific climate change-related perceptions (Marczak et al., 2023; Pihkala, 2022). Negative emotions related to climate change seem to be more prevalent in research, including emotions such as fear, worry, grief, guilt, shame, anger, or disgust. Positive emotions related to climate change are urge to act, joy, pride, optimism, or compassion. In classifying and measuring climate-related emotions, we suggest following the inventory of climate emotions which captures

Engagement Dimension	Concept	Description and Relevant Research
		eight emotions: anger, contempt, enthusiasm, powerlessness, guilt, isolation, anxiety, and sorrow (Marczak et al., 2023). Individuals experiencing climate-related emotions tend to also support climate policies and report more pro-environmental behaviour.
Cognitive Climate Change Engagement	Self-assessed climate change knowledge	We suggest using self-assessed knowledge because we don't expect the game-based tools to convey climate science facts, which are usually part of knowledge questionnaires; see Player et al., 2023). While self-assessed knowledge often correlated with factual knowledge, respondents who identify as male, older, and college-educated tend to report higher self-assessed understanding, even if their factual knowledge is not higher than other respondents' (Hamilton, 2018). Likewise, conservative respondents show no or a negative association between self-assessed and factual knowledge. These findings suggest that self-assessed knowledge might be influenced by a person's confidence, self-image, or worldview. However, self-assessed knowledge can be a stronger predictor than factual knowledge when it comes to lifestyle and political behaviours for the environment (Howansky et al., 2010).
	Belief in human-made climate change	The belief that climate change is really occurring and that human activity is the main cause. Believing in climate change is an important determinant of many of the other measures we propose for the participant evaluation, such as knowledge, concern, pro-environmental behavioural intentions, but also climate policy support (Hornsey et al., 2016; Kotchen et al., 2013; Perera et al., 2022; Sibley & Kurz, 2013).
	Self-efficacy	Self-efficacy is a concept proposed by Bandura (1997) and describes the individual's belief or confidence in their own capability to perform a given behaviour and achieve an intended outcome. Self-efficacy beliefs develop based on perception and reflection and represent processes of self-regulation and controlling one's actions. It is an important factor in any kind of learning, in addition to determining whether an individual will exercise a given behaviour. As self-efficacy is domain-specific, we also propose specific self-efficacy concepts for GREAT.
	Political self-efficacy	Political self-efficacy consists of internal and external dimensions of political efficacy: internal efficacy refers to feeling capable of understanding and effectively participating in political processes and external efficacy to the belief that political institutions will respond to these participation

Engagement Dimension	Concept	Description and Relevant Research
		<p>efforts (see Niemi et al., 1991). For instance, internal political efficacy might capture whether an individual feels that they are well-qualified for participating in political matters or whether they feel confident when discussing politics with others (Scotto et al., 2021). External political efficacy can include the individual's feeling that they don't have any say in what the government does or that they have many ways to influence what the government does. Those who report to have high political efficacy are usually more active in online and offline political participation (Oser et al., 2022).</p>
	Self-efficacy for climate action	<p>Associated with Those with higher self-efficacy regarding climate action and environmental behaviours also tend to show more mitigation and adaptation actions, pro-environmental behavioural intentions, policy support, and collective action (Kothe et al., 2023; Lubell, 2002; Lubell et al., 2007; Ung et al., 2015). They are more likely to engage in discussions of climate change with strangers, family or friends (Geiger et al., 2017; Tian et al., 2023). If individuals show strong climate anxiety, self-efficacy can support them in taking action (Innocenti et al., 2023).</p>
	Collective efficacy for climate action	<p>Describes the belief that one's group has the capabilities of achieving a common goal (Bandura, 2000; Roser-Renouf et al., 2014). This concept accounts for the fact that members of a group or society are interconnected and that some goals are only attainable through joint efforts. As the climate crisis is a global issue, the belief that concerted efforts and collective action can successfully solve climate change is assumed to be vital for any individual to engage in action (Koletsou & Mancy, 2011). Individuals with higher collective efficacy beliefs tend to show higher policy support, are more involved in community adaptation measures as well as in collective action (Thaker et al., 2016, 2019; Van Zomeren et al., 2008).</p>
Behavioural climate change engagement	Collective action intentions	<p>Collective action behaviours include activism or different forms of political participation (see Ballew et al., 2019; Lubell et al., 2007). It's important to measure intentions rather than reported past behaviour, as a) it is unrealistic that actual behaviour will change right after an intervention and b) self-reports of past behaviours are not accurate measures of actual behaviour, as they tend to be systematically biased e.g., by social desirability (Koller et al., 2023; Kormos & Gifford, 2014; Lange & Dewitte, 2019).</p>

Table 1. Overview and description of relevant constructs for climate change engagement.

6.2 Game-based Approaches for Climate Change

Game-based formats for public engagement might offer potential to overcome some of the barriers already discussed and expand traditional engagement activities to involve a wider public in climate policy, as suggested by several reviews (Fernández Galeote et al., 2021; Loh, 2019; Thiel et al., 2016). In this research, game elements are incorporated in engagement formats to make participation more interesting and enjoyable, drawing a broader audience of citizens, allowing citizens to experience and explore solutions in simulated environments, and simply make participation more fun. For instance, Foxman & Forelle (2014) investigated how a “fantasy election”, imitating a fantasy football league but with candidates for congressional and presidential elections in the US with points and awards, improved willingness to vote, whereas (Gordon & Schirra (2011) explored the use of PC life simulation game in a community planning process, whereby players took on the role of different avatars representing different residents’ needs who have to fulfil quests.

In general, interest in these game-based methods is informed by the notion that games are enjoyable, increase motivation and attention, allow players to learn in a simulated environment through their own decisions and actions, and enable social interactions with virtual characters or other players (Douglas & Brauer, 2021; Fernández Galeote et al., 2021; Katsaliaki & Mustafee, 2015; Wu & Lee, 2015). Several studies suggest that players experience game-based approaches covering climate change as enjoyable, entertaining, and interesting, though playing can also result negative experiences such as confusion, frustration, or perceiving the game-based tool as providing no personal value (Fernández Galeote et al., 2021). Moreover, some participants perceived games as inappropriate tool for addressing serious issues such as climate change. Tools with technical issues or unappealing graphics can also lead to a negative experience.

For understanding the elements used in the game-based tools developed by the great project, we follow the categorization by Fernández Galeote et al. (2021) who reviewed an extensive corpus of game-based interventions for improving climate change engagement. They distinguish four main categories of game elements: **achievement- and progression-oriented**; **social-oriented**; **immersion-oriented**; and the use of **representation, resources and materials** (Fernández Galeote et al., 2021, p. 10). The four categories of game elements including examples are outlined in Table 2.

Game Element Category	Description	Example Game Elements
Achievement- and progression-oriented game elements	Quantification of players' progress	Quests, levels, feedback statistics, points and scores, badges, timer and speed limits
Social-oriented game elements	Enabling social interactions and relationships between players	Cooperation and collaboration, collective voting, social networking features, peer-ratings
Immersion-oriented game elements	Drawing and retaining the player into the game world	Role plays, narratives and storytelling, player character/avatar
Representation, resources, and materials	Digital, physical, or human game contents extending the main game	Facilitators/moderators, physical playboards, physical cards, digital objects

Table 2. Description of game elements according to Fernández Galeote et al. (2021, p. 10).

Notably, despite these existing categorisations of game elements, evidence on how game elements are related to climate change engagement is scarce, including the mechanisms, which dimensions of engagement are affected how, or which elements are most effective in which situations. An unsystematic review suggests that the quantification of achievements (e.g., by providing performance statistics or awarding points) and facilitating social interactions (e.g., through storylines and narratives, role play, cooperation, or peer-rating) are particularly effective game elements for promoting personal climate change engagement, but an evidence base for drawing strong conclusion is lacking (Fernández Galeote et al., 2021).

6.3 Evaluation and Impact Assessment

GREAT seeks to involve a wide range of stakeholders in different phases of its research cycle, incorporating elements of participatory research, co-creation, and citizen social science (see Albert et al., 2021 for an overview of these concepts). Accordingly, we based the evaluation methodology for GREAT on the **open framework for evaluating citizen science** developed by Kieslinger et al. (2018). This framework covers three dimensions to identify and assess a project's impacts: 1) the scientific impact, 2) the individual actors (participants), and 3) the socio-ecological and economic dimension (Kieslinger et al., 2018). The scientific dimension of impact is concerned with academic standards like scientific knowledge production and dissemination, the provision of new knowledge resources, and the opening of new research questions and research fields. The dimension of individual actors involved in the project focusses on their gains from participating in project activities, such as improved skills, knowledge, or awareness on the topic covered. The socio-ecological and economic dimension covers the wider contexts in which a project is situated and how the project activities and outcomes influence the societal, ecological, and economic systems it is embedded in (see Figure 1 for an overview).

Figure 1: Citizen Science Evaluation Framework by Kieslinger et al. (2018)

In the context of GREAT, we distinguish the **scientific, economic, and societal dimension of impacts**. It is important to note that non-researchers involved in research projects enter with their own goals, interests, or needs. Taking these into account can benefit the definition and evaluation of project outcomes, which is termed co-evaluation (Kieslinger, Schürz, et al., 2022). In co-evaluation, the actors involved in a project are also involved in its evaluation process and contribute to defining the project objectives and expected impact.

They also contribute to iteratively examining whether these objectives are being reached, and which intended and unintended impacts are traceable. Implementing co-evaluation principles (Kieslinger, Mayer, et al., 2022) is beneficial for understanding the social and societal impacts of research projects and facilitating and opening the processes of research and knowledge production. However, it is also challenging as everyone involved needs to take on new roles; researchers have the tasks of communicating, facilitating, and managing expectations whereas citizens and other stakeholders need to deal with principles of the scientific process and practice. In the evaluation of the GREAT project, co-evaluation principles will be implemented in certain but not all stages of the research and evaluation process. More specifically, the evaluation will involve key stakeholders in defining expectations and objectives of the evaluation as well as jointly interpret the evaluation results to draw conclusions regarding its impacts and accomplishment of objectives.

The **logic model framework** (see Figure 2) can be used to represent the logical relationships between a project's inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts (Kurz & Kubek, 2017; Roberts, 1998). It is widely used for assessing the impact of projects in different domains.

Figure 2: Logic Model Scheme

- Input: available resources and efforts, like expertise, materials, equipment, or software
- Activities: actions planned to achieve desired outputs
- Outputs: immediate products or services resulting from activities, such as data points collected, workshops conducted
- Outcomes: effects of outputs on target group involved or addressed during the project, such as behaviour change, knowledge or skills
- Impact: long-term changes on a societal or system level; progress made towards high-level goals; typically achieved beyond project or programme lifetime

Thus, project evaluations usually focus on measuring the outputs and outcomes, which are assumed to later result in long-term, wider impacts. By applying the logic model, we collect evidence that give good indications that the impact will be reached (or not).

For the GREAT evaluation, we developed logic models covering the dimensions outlined in the open framework for citizen science while considering co-evaluation principles. Four logic models for the participant, scientific, societal, and economic dimensions are presented in the next chapter.

6.4 Summary of Theoretical Framework

We conclude this chapter by combining the different approaches discussed above into one theoretical framework for evaluating the game-based tools developed in the GREAT project. The objective of the GREAT evaluation is studying the social use and impact of the GREAT game-based tools and to provide evidence of game-based participatory processes. This theoretical framework provides the basis for this objective and a) informs the research methodology; b) informs the interpretation of evaluation results and c) allows to connect the evaluation results with previous research on game-based approaches as well as situating the GREAT project in this research landscape. A summary of this theoretical framework is presented in Figure 3.

In this theoretical framework, we understand the Playmob quiz tool as communication or consultation engagement, as it is participants are engaged individually by providing opinions and preferences (Reed et al., 2018). The DIBL dilemma game is characterised by discussion and collective voting on policy options, with the goal of developing a joint strategy, which is why we understand it as the deliberation or co-production type of engagement. Further, GREAT will engage citizens, policymakers, and other climate stakeholders as co-researchers (e.g., in intervention design, evaluation design, or data analysis). Further, we include the categorisation of game elements by Fernández Galeote et al. (2021) in our framework to describe the game-based tools developed within GREAT; we expect the game-based tools to contain achievement-and progress-oriented, social-oriented, and immersion-oriented elements as well as representation, resources, and materials. We expect that the types of engagement implemented within GREAT, enhanced with game elements in the case of communication/consultation and deliberation/co-production, will influence cognitive, affective, and behavioural climate change engagement as key outcomes. In addition, we expect that co-researchers and co-evaluators will have personal gains, such as improved skills, from their participation.

Overall, the engagement and research activities within GREAT are expected to contribute to wider impacts on the scientific, economic, and societal dimension. These types of engagement, the use of game elements, improvements of engagement outcomes, and contributions to wider impacts are contingent on underlying processes and experiences of the participants involved. Specifically, the extent to which participants experience the engagement as inclusive, how they perceive the exchange of information and learning, how they assess their influence on political decisions and how they experience the game-based tools play a role in the success of the project activities and will feed into the evaluation.

Figure 3: The theoretical framework forming the basis for the GREAT project evaluation

7 Research and Evaluation Methodology

This chapter describes the methodological framework proposed to structure and systematically evaluate the GREAT project and gauge its potential impact. We first describe the four logic models, followed by the specific research designs to be applied to the GREAT case studies. The proposed evaluation methodologies are informed by the theoretical framework discussed in the previous chapter.

While we have provided detailed research designs, methods, and evaluation instruments in this deliverable, case study leaders are **not** expected to apply all methods to their case studies or measure all concepts. Rather, a **selection** of methods and concepts should be applied. Thus, at the beginning of a case study, the responsible project partner is encouraged to meet with the ZSI team as leaders of WP5 (responsible for Evaluation and Impact Assessment) to discuss which methods and measures to apply and how the evaluation can be implemented. The possibility of involving case study partners such as policymakers or citizens as co-researchers and co-evaluators should also be discussed.

The evaluation instruments, especially the questionnaires provided in Annexes 10, 11 and 12 have all been pre-tested with 2 senior researchers from ZSI. The results of the cognitive pre-testing were documented by the GREAT research team and adapted according to the provided feedback.

7.1 The GREAT Logic Models

The project Grant Agreement defines the activities, outputs, and objectives of GREAT, which provides basic input for the GREAT logic models. In addition, consortium partners discussed their expectations and aims for the project outcomes and impacts (i.e., expected changes two years after the project) along the core target groups (citizens and gamers; domain experts; the gaming industry; policymakers, NGOs, and campaigning organisations; and project partners) in a workshop during the first consortium meeting. The information from these two sources populated the first version of the logic models for the participant dimension, scientific dimension, and socio-economic dimension.

The first pilot cycle of the GREAT project included workshops with policy representatives and stakeholders from Frankfurt to discuss climate policy issues. We also asked about their expectations from the GREAT project and compared and matched those with the outcomes in our logic models. Further, advanced versions of the logic models were presented and discussed with consortium partners. These discussions resulted in the GREAT logic models as presented below.

7.1.1 Participant dimension of GREAT

Figure 4: Logic model for assessing the participant dimension

The target groups relevant for this dimension consist of those individuals involved in GREAT activities (i.e., by playing the game-based tools or in participatory activities) as well as citizens more generally, when considering long-term impacts. The available inputs for the activities are coming from the consortium partners, such as experience in citizen science and co-design approaches or existing game prototypes and platforms. As Figure 4 shows, we expect to have a considerable number of participants from different cultural and geographical backgrounds involved as an output. The involvement can range from co-research activities, such as the participation in co-design of case study or in a data analysis activity (see steps in the GREAT research cycle). The larger number of citizens will be involved as players in the GREAT game-based tools.

Overall, on the participant side, we expect that through the implementation of the game-based tools, citizens have new means of expressing their opinions and participating in policy decisions. As an important outcome on the participants side, we also expect an improved knowledge, understanding, awareness, and attitudes. Finally, in the long-term and beyond the project runtime the GREAT activities expected to have contributed to the expectation and vision defined in the project, such as more diverse and accessible channels for political and societal participation, citizens' empowerment and feeling of being heard in political decision-making, easier opportunities for citizens to participate in the political discussion and policy through new formats and tools, and to citizens' increased interest in climate change topics and their willingness to participate in climate policy decisions.

7.1.2 Scientific dimension of GREAT

Figure 5: Logic model for the scientific dimension

The target groups of the scientific dimension are GREAT project partners, domain experts and researchers, as well as the scientific community at large. The consortium partners bring in extensive expertise, tools and methods for realising the planned activities and reaching the expected outcomes. Next to the inter-disciplinary research expertise we also count the game engines and platforms provided by the GREAT commercial partners Playmob and Serious Games Interactive as important input. Next to the quantified scientific output of academic publications we also expect methodological insights and technological advances. The GREAT outputs including the publications, a possible toolkit, different research and design outputs will be available to everyone via open access publication (this includes outputs on the games, methods, technical infrastructure and analytical tools and the data collected, as far as this is possible while staying anonymous). We also expect that the GREAT methodology informs future research about citizen science approaches in game design and the climate crisis.

Overall, the research activities in GREAT are expected to contribute to an ongoing research agenda within the scientific community by developing and sharing new information, experiences, and questions; the development and validation of the GREAT games will also provide new means for raising awareness and reaching new target groups not addressed with previous methods. Moreover, the GREAT research activities will contribute to new knowledge on citizen science methods and how they can be applied, provided to the project partners, domain experts, and the scientific community at large. In terms of long-term impacts, we expect that the GREAT experiences can contribute to promoting a better understanding of gaming as a communication channel for reaching diverse target groups and to a new understanding of how games-based approaches can be used as engaging tools for awareness raising, as research tools, and for citizen science.

7.1.3 Economic dimension of GREAT

Figure 6: Logic model for economic deminsion

The main target groups for the economic dimension of GREAT are the commercial project partners Playmob and Serious Games Interactive as well as the gaming industry more generally. Building on the experiences of the commercial partners and their networks, the GREAT activities are expected to gain insights and bring forward new applications or features, methods, products, and services that contribute to the business propositions of our partners and can potentially be leveraged by the gaming industry. We expect our commercial partners to expand their portfolio by providing the new products and services that have been developed in the context of the project. An important success factor to reach the expected outcomes and impact of GREAT on the gaming industry will be the active engagement with representatives from the gaming industry, which is a highly dynamic space to operate in.

In the long-term, we expect GREAT to contribute to shaping new visions for game-based approaches and the games sector, where stakeholders will start to perceive social and political action as valuable additions in games and generate socially valuable outputs. More specifically, the commercial partners in GREAT continue running successful businesses, have more opportunities for public-private partnerships and gain new clients in the public sector as we expect new connections between the commercial partners in GREAT and other groups and stakeholders who wish to engage with games, such as NGOs or policymakers.

7.1.4 Societal dimension of GREAT

Figure 7: Logic model for societal dimension

The main target groups for the social dimension of GREAT are policymakers, NGOs, campaigning organisations, and society at large. As the GREAT consortium already have some established relationships with policy stakeholders and public institutions, we start from a strong foundation to engage these stakeholders. The stakeholder engagement is crucial for the citizen science approach in game design as well as in the research cycle, involving policy stakeholders in GREAT research activities (e.g., for developing policy issues addressed by the games), the evaluation of GREAT regarding its contribution to social inclusion, public engagement, and political participation, and the different communication and dissemination activities.

At societal level we expect the GREAT outcomes to be of considerable value for policy makers, public organisations and NGOs, as we offer insights and a new method to engage with citizens for targeted communication, participation, engagement, and opinion gathering. In addition, we expect that the GREAT toolkit and policy briefs will provide policymakers, NGOs, and campaigning organisations with a new understanding of the potential of games for societal change and transformation.

In the long-term we can envision that GREAT games will be adopted within different institutions such as schools and by policy bodies, in addition to being accepted as communication medium and channel for public policy and public sector engagement by policymakers. Due to our project activities and outcomes, we also hope that the GREAT games will inspire new formats of political participation for EU citizens. Moreover, because of the games, policymakers, NGOs, and campaigning organisations will have a better understanding of citizens' preferences and ideas. And overall, among different stakeholders and society at large, there will hopefully be a growing knowledge and consciousness about the social impact of games.

These four logic models offer a scheme for structuring and understanding the objectives of GREAT and the means through which they will be achieved. As such, it also allows monitoring the timely and successful delivery of the planned activities and outputs; only if these are successful, we can achieve the expected outcomes. Therefore, the planned activities and outputs will also be monitored as part of the evaluation. The next sections will describe the methodology and research designs for assessing the expected outcomes.

7.2 Assessing the Participant Dimension

In GREAT, participants can be involved in three main activities which differ in content, implementation, and objectives. Therefore, we developed a distinct evaluation methodology for participants in each activity to account for their different objectives and principles:

- Methods for assessing participants in a DIBL dilemma game;
- Methods for assessing participants in a Playmob quiz;
- and methods for assessing participatory activities (e.g., citizen science activities or activities along the research cycle).

The methods and proposed evaluation instruments should be adapted to the specific case study and research questions.

7.2.1 Methods for assessing participants in a DIBL dilemma game

The assessment of participants playing the DIBL dilemma game will utilise multiple methods and approaches, as players' identity will usually be known, allowing us to approach them for pre- and follow-up data collection. A pre-/post-design allows to assess changes in participants' outcomes that can attributed to their participation, even though we cannot establish causal relationships due to the lack of a control group. We expect that participating in the DIBL dilemma game will contribute to all four outcomes in the participant logic model: **participants have personal gains in knowledge, understanding, awareness, and attitudes; participants have new means of expressing opinions; participants have new means of participating in policy decisions; participants positively evaluate their involvement in GREAT.** For assessing these outcomes, we refer to our theoretical framework (see Figure 3) and propose to assess participants' personal climate change engagement (affective, cognitive, and behavioural), their experience of the game along public engagement process criteria, and their game experience.

Figure 8 present the overall research methodology and generalised research workflow for participant playing the DIBL dilemma game, which might be adapted to the specific of the case study und evaluation. We suggest using the DIBL system for evaluation data collection, as it allows to connect all of the data collected in the different steps while avoiding switching between tools and platforms. However, using the DIBL system requires to collect data from the pre-questionnaire to the debriefing in one session.

In general, the research design assumes that participants join the game either being invited to a session or by being engaged spontaneously at a game session, for instance during a conference or fair. In both cases, participants would join a session and upon attending, would be provided with a pre-questionnaire, in addition to completing the informed consent form. Afterwards, the game session starts and participants play the game. When the game ends, participants will receive the post-questionnaire on their individual devices and will be asked to complete the questions. The game session concludes with a short debriefing discussion moderated by the facilitator(s), which invites participants to reflect on their experiences during the game, share insights, and address any other concerns which arose during the game. Finally, based on the conclusions drawn from in-game data, questionnaire, and debriefing, selected participants might be invited to join a focus group discussion and further reflect and discuss their experience, allowing the GREAT researchers a more in-depth investigation of why and how playing impacted participants.

Figure 8: Research design for assessing participants playing the dilemma game.

The **participant pre- and post-questionnaire** will be a main tool to assess how playing the game might be associated with changes in participants' key outcome measures. We suggest using as outcome measures a selection of existing scales for affective, cognitive, and behavioural climate change engagement we provided in Appendix A. We also suggest to include several sociodemographic questions allowing for comparisons between participants. As already discussed, the scales should ideally be selected in a co-evaluation process involving the ZSI team, the project partners responsible for the case study, and other stakeholders involved in the case study. Further, the selection of scales should be based on the case study's research question and consider the burden placed on participants.

The purpose of the **debriefing and discussion guideline** is to equip DIBL facilitators with a structured set of questions to capture a) participants' experiences and engagement during the gameplay and b) their perception of criteria used to evaluate public engagement processes (see Appendix A). The guideline uses a mix of closed-ended and open-ended questions, which should be implemented with an interactive survey tool and facilitated group discussions. The closed-ended questions can be used to quickly capture players' responses, which can then be visualised to promote the discussion by the facilitator. Additionally, the facilitator can use open-ended questions to capture participants' thoughts and experiences more in-depth. Like the other evaluation instruments, the debriefing and discussion guideline can be used as a modular guideline and adapted to the needs of the case study. In general, the discussions should be recorded by the facilitator(s) using audio recording or notes.

For assessing game experience and engagement, we provide four closed-ended questions adapted from Nussbaum et al. (2016) answered on a 6-point Likert scale and one open-ended question covering participants' general experience with the game specifically. Subsequently, the guideline provides questions about experiencing playing along the criteria of a public engagement process. These questions were adapted from Schroeter et al. (2016) and focus on two criteria: *inclusiveness* and *information exchange and learning* (see section 6.1.1). We chose these two criteria as they account for the discussion-based approach of DIBL which centers around social interaction and collective exchange. While the framework by Schroeter et al. (2016) was developed based on theoretical analysis and empirical findings as well as tested, the authors only provide snippets of their evaluation results and measurement instruments, which we adapted to assess the dilemma game.

We suggest measuring inclusiveness with three closed-ended questions asking about equal contribution during discussions, whether the content of an argument was more important than the person saying it, and whether the discussions allowed for exchanging diverging opinions. For measuring information exchange and learning, we suggest using one closed-ended question asking whether participants had enough information for making choices, and three open-ended questions asking about new perspectives or ideas they learned about, their expectations about participation and whether these were met, and finally, about any other feedback about their participation. For their instrument, Schroeter et al. (2016) used an 8 point scale but did not provide the labels. Therefore, we opted for consistency and suggest using the same 6-point Likert scale used for measuring game engagement.

Finally, we suggest to conduct **focus groups** with selected participants to capture their shared experience of playing, including collective processes of discussion and reflection (see Morgan, 1998). For participants, playing the game is a collective experience characterised by joint decision and voting. Focus group as an evaluation method draws from these shared experiences to explore how participants perceived and interpreted their session, why they acted in a specific way, and how it influenced them in the aftermath. The sampling strategy should be adapted to the case study and research interests, but generally offers several options. Groups could be composed of participants from the same game session or from different sessions or based on similarities or diversity in their questionnaire responses. While the sampling strategy can be adapted, it should always be well justified. We prepared a general focus guideline covering different dimensions (such as cognitive, affective, and behavioural climate change engagement) which can be modified to fit the specific case study and research question. Our design of the focus group guidelines follows the structure suggested by Hennink (2007), which consists of four main elements: introducing the setting, opening up the discussion, investigating the main research topic, and summarising and concluding the discussion.

7.2.2 Methods for assessing participants in a Playmob quiz

The general research methodology for assessing participants playing the Playmob quiz is presented in Figure 9. Individuals playing a Playmob quiz will be sampled through an in-game ad or through sharing a link to the quiz via social media, posting flyers, or mailing lists. The sample size for each quiz will be determined for each distribution separately and depends on the specific case study and the target group, but we expect each distribution to sample at least a thousand participants up to several ten thousands or even hundred thousands.

We propose to assess quiz participants regarding the following logic model outcomes: **participants positively evaluate their involvement in GREAT; participants have new means of expressing opinions; participants have new means of participating in policy decisions; participants have personal gains in knowledge, understanding, awareness, and attitudes.** We propose to operationalise these outcomes by using the concepts of personal climate change engagement, criteria for public engagement processes, as well as game engagement.

Similar to the DIBL game evaluation, the evaluation of quiz participants will depend on how the implementation of the specific quiz and the research questions guiding the related case study. However, we developed a generalised research methodology which can be adapted to the quiz implementation (see Figure 9). The research design follows the pre-determined quiz flow and assumes that participants start their participation by receiving the quiz as an in-game ad or through a link. They open up the quiz and complete the quiz questions. After they have finished, they can be provided with one open-ended evaluation question asking about their experience during responding to the quiz. Then, players are asked if they want to see the results of the quiz and upon confirmation, redirected to a data dashboard providing a visualisation of the results. They are asked to sign up into an online community of gamers interested in climate change; if they sign up, they can then be provided with a questionnaire to capture their experience more in-depth. If possible, a sample of other community members who have not joined through the quiz could be surveyed for comparison.

Figure 9: Research design for assessing participants playing the quiz game.

As the **quiz tool** captures not participants’ direct responses to the questions but also meta-data such as time spent on a question, at which question they drop-out or whether they complete the quiz, we suggest using this data as an indicator for participants’ engagement during the quiz and the extent to which they experienced their participation as positive.

We propose including one open-ended **post-question** after the main question to capture participants’ immediate thoughts about their experience. This open-ended question is designed to emphasise the reflection of the quiz experience, provide an in-depth indicator of participants’ experiences while playing and how it might contribute to key outcomes of interest for the specific case study. We have prepared open-ended questions for measuring affective, cognitive, and behavioural climate change engagement as well as participants’ assessment of the quiz as public

engagement tool. This question captures participants' perceived *influence on political decisions* as one criterion for engagement processes (Schroeter et al., 2016).

Further, the **post-questionnaire** distributed among members of the online community can be used to get a broader overview of participants' climate change engagement in comparison with other community members (who have not joined the community through the quiz) or over time (i.e., collect data at several points in time). We suggest using the existing scales for measuring climate change engagement provided in Appendix A. Relevant scales should be selected in tandem with the ZSI team and case study representatives as well as their external partners based on the specific case study and its research questions.

7.2.3 Methods for assessing participatory activities

Those individuals participating in a participatory activity in the context of GREAT, such as a workshop on a local policy dilemma, a workshop for game design, or a data sprint will be either directly invited to join (e.g., through personal contacts or specialised mailing lists) or will learn about the event through an open call that could be advertised through social media, flyers, or posters. We expect that the number of participants who will join will vary with a maximum of 30 participants per event. We expect that participation in a GREAT event will promote the following outcomes in the participant logic model: participants will have **personal gains** (i.e., in knowledge, understanding, awareness, or attitudes, depending on the type of event) and will **positively evaluate their involvement in the GREAT activity**.

Figure 10: Research design for assessing participants involved in citizen science activities

The general research methodology for assessing participants in cycle activities (e.g., workshops and other participatory activities) is presented in Figure 10. The main assessment method is a debriefing and group discussion to reflect on participants' experiences, which will be implemented by facilitators after the main activity is completed.

In citizen science projects, individual learning outcomes of participants are among the most commonly assessed criteria, including improved skills and knowledge or awareness on the topic of the activity (Jordan et al., 2012; Kieslinger et al., 2017; Phillips et al., 2014). To assess the extent to which the participatory activities and workshops in GREAT can contribute to relevant learning outcomes, we also suggest measuring whether participants feel that they **improved knowledge and skills** of scientific analysis (for participants in data sprints), technical and computer skills (for participants engaged in game design or development), or policy processes (for participants in workshops on climate policy issues). Moreover, participants will be asked to indicate any other **perceived gains** from their participation, whether they **enjoyed** the activity and which parts they liked most. Participants will also be asked to provide general feedback on the activity.

We provided a **debriefing and discussion guideline** for participatory activities in Appendix A, which captures perceptions of improved knowledge and skills, gains from participation, and enjoyment of the activity. It consists of a mix of open-ended and closed-ended questions. The open-ended questions will be asked by the facilitator to prompt a moderated discussion in the group, whereas the closed-ended questions will be posed by using an interactive survey tool (e.g., DIBL, Kahoot quiz, or Mentimeter). The discussion within the group will need to be recorded by the facilitator(s), whereas the responses in the interactive survey tool will be saved automatically for further analysis. Questions about participants' improvements in skills and knowledge can be adapted based on the specific workshop contents. In the guideline, we provided questions specific for workshops about climate change issues or dilemmas; game design or development; and data sprints.

7.3 Assessing the Scientific Dimension

For assessing the scientific dimension, we will use two main methods: 1) indicators tracking metrics of scientific activities and outputs and 2) primary data collection. The quality and reach of scientific outputs is often assessed using the journal impact factor, which has been criticised for its bias and limitations (Cagan, 2013).

The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) suggests considering all types of research outputs, shifting the focus from the journal impact to the potential impact of the research on policy and practice. Following these recommendations and considering our logic model, we have chosen indicators which go beyond academic citations by examining the scientific activities, a range of different scientific outputs (including software, data, or preprints), and metrics of outreach and dissemination. Tools from altmetrics (<http://altmetrics.org/tools/>) can support tracking and assessing how research resulting from the GREAT project is received and discussed across different websites and platforms, including outputs such as slides and datasets. These quantitative indicators are complemented by qualitative evidence collected from GREAT project partners during workshops held at consortium meetings to reflect on the project and its scientific impact. If necessary, for better understanding scientific impacts, we will also conduct qualitative interviews with experts in the domains of survey methodology, citizen science, climate change, or climate policy towards the end of the project. The indicators were inspired by the reviews of citizen science evaluation criteria in Kieslinger et al. (2017) and Jordan et al. (2012).

Table 3 provides an overview of indicators and methods applied to assess the outcomes defined in the GREAT logic model on scientific impact.

Scientific Outcomes	Quantitative metrics	Qualitative data
<p>new survey methodology for opinions and attitudes in different research domains</p> <p>new information and data on the climate crisis for domain experts</p> <p>contribution to an ongoing research agenda by developing new information, experiences, and questions</p> <p>new means for raising awareness and reaching specific target groups (based on socio-demographic characteristics such as gender, age, or economic resources)</p> <p>new knowledge on citizen science and its application among the scientific community, domain experts, and project partners</p>	<p># of Playmob quizzes implemented</p> <p># of DIBL dilemma games implemented</p> <p>Topics and themes covered in quiz questions and in dilemma games (numbers and contents)</p> <p># of academic publications (conferences, peer-reviewed journals)</p> <p># of citations in other academic outputs</p> <p># of views, downloads, tweets, or posts of academic outputs, deliverables, datasets, and other research materials (as indicated by Researchgate, Zenodo, or altmetrics tools)</p> <p># of collaborations with researchers from institutions outside the GREAT consortium</p> <p># and types of target groups reached with GREAT activities (games, citizen science, dissemination & exploitation)</p> <p># of GREAT publications on citizen science and their outreach (academic publications, blogs, news, social media posts)</p>	<p>2 reflection workshops with project partners during consortium meetings</p> <p>3-5 qualitative interviews with experts in survey methodology, citizen science, climate change, or climate policy towards the end of the project</p>

Table 3: Scientific impact assessment

7.4 Assessing the Economic dimension

We will use three types of indicators to assess the economic dimension of GREAT (see Table 4):

- indicators covering dissemination and communication activities
- indicators about target groups engaged during the project
- indicators regarding the game elements developed within the project

All project partners will support the evaluation team with collecting data to inform the indicators. We will assess the outcome of the open access elements provided online by GREAT partners and the downloads, views, and shares (i.e., online engagement). Similar to the assessment of the scientific dimension, tools like those on altmetrics (<http://altmetrics.org/tools/>) might be used to track engagement, in addition to using metrics on the open access platforms where GREAT contributions will be posted. Moreover, the GREAT commercial partners can provide additional information based on their interactions with representatives from the gaming industry. We will follow up with the GREAT commercial partners to assess in how far they can expand their portfolio and provide new products and services by looking at the new game features developed during GREAT. The innovativeness of these features will be assessed in discussions within the consortium and possible feedback from commercial partners.

We will also have a close look at the target groups that were involved in GREAT either by playing the games or by co-designing the games or game elements to find indications of reaching new use cases and target groups. Finally, we will have a look at dissemination metrics, specifically the number of presentations the commercial partners gave about GREAT, and the number of inquiries commercial partners received about GREAT through email or social media.

Economic outcomes	Dissemination & Communication Indicators	Target Group Indicators	Game elements Indicators
<p>a new, innovative approach for game development which can be used by the gaming industry (e.g., involvement of citizens in the process, using games for benefitting society)</p> <p>GREAT commercial partners can expand their portfolio and provide new products and services</p> <p>gaming industry and games companies have access to new use cases and target groups</p> <p>connections between GREAT commercial partners and groups who wish to engage with gamers</p>	<p># of open access game elements distributed and their engagement</p> <p># of presentations by GREAT commercial partners</p> <p># of inquiries about GREAT received by commercial partners</p>	<p># and type of target groups engaged in playing the games</p> <p># and type of target groups engaged in co-designing content and game elements</p>	<p># of game elements developed within GREAT</p> <p># and innovativeness of new game elements developed within GREAT</p>

Table 4: Indicators for assessing the economic dimension

7.5 Assessing the Societal Dimension

The assessment of the societal dimension will focus on interactions with policy stakeholders such as policymakers, NGOs, campaigning organisations, or climate policy experts. Thus, we will conduct qualitative interviews with policy stakeholders to elicit their perspectives on the GREAT method for citizen communication and engagement and the potential of games for promoting social change. Part of the interviews will also include discussing citizens' recommendations for addressing the climate crisis, based on results from engagement activities in the case studies. These reflections with policy stakeholders are an integral part of the GREAT research cycle (see the different stages of the GREAT case study cycle in Del 4.1 and 4.2). The concept of policy learning will be used for understanding policy representatives perspectives on citizens' recommendations, which comprises perceived improvements regarding factual knowledge, changes in norms, values and beliefs, and changes in common understanding and trust in the context of a given policy issue (see Huitema et al., 2010). Accordingly, both the citizens and the policymakers participating in an engagement process can improve their policy learning. For policymakers, policy learning based on citizens' recommendations might include learning new factual information; new insights into policy dilemmas, which may lead to questioning their own points of view; and better understanding and relating with citizens' issues. The qualitative interviews will be conducted towards the end of the project. Moreover, results from participants' evaluation of the DIBL dilemma game as a public engagement process will also inform the value of the GREAT method for communication, participation, and engagement.

We also expect that representatives from the gaming industry, policy stakeholders, and climate experts will positively evaluate the GREAT insight reports. Feedback on those insights will be directly gathered during the presentations towards these target groups, mostly policy makers that have been involved during the case studies and will reflect on the policy dilemmas covered in each case. Next to the direct feedback we may also collect written feedback about the insight reports from targeted stakeholders.

To assess the reach of the indicated number of stakeholders and policy bodies we will analyse a set of artefacts, such as written communication (e.g., emails) received by GREAT partners from policy bodies or stakeholder organisations will be analysed as well as these organisations’ news items, blog articles, reports, or social media posts, if they had contact with the GREAT consortium during the project duration. In addition, project partners will share their experiences with policy bodies and stakeholder organisations regarding interest about adopting the GREAT methods during reflection workshops held during in-person consortium meetings.

Societal outcomes	Interviews with policy stakeholders	Collecting information on policy bodies and stakeholder organisations	Reflection workshops with partners
<p>new method targeting citizens for policymakers, NGOs, or campaigning organisations of using games as a tool for communication, participation, engagement and gathering opinions on current issues</p> <p>policymakers, NGOs, or campaigning organisations have a new understanding of the potential of games for societal change and transformation</p> <p>representatives from the gaming industry, policy stakeholders, and climate experts positively evaluate the GREAT insight reports</p> <p>a minimum of 30 policy bodies take steps to adopt the GREAT methods and business models</p> <p>a minimum of 25 stakeholder organisations express intentions to adopt the GREAT methods</p>	<p>GREAT method for citizen communication and engagement</p> <p>The potential of games for social change</p> <p>Discussion of citizens’ policy recommendations and perspectives on policy learning (from case studies step 8)</p> <p>Disseminating and collecting feedback on the insight reports from representatives from the gaming industry, policy stakeholders, climate crisis campaigners, and green policy stakeholders</p>	<p>GREAT is mentioned in their news items, blog articles, reports, or social media posts</p> <p>GREAT partners receive inquiries from policy bodies or stakeholder organisations</p>	<p>2 reflection workshops with project partners during consortium meetings</p>

Table 5: Indicators for assessing the societal dimension

8 Summary and Outlook

Evaluation and impact assessment approaches in citizen science have advanced significantly over the last years. While traditionally projects were mostly assessing their academic output in terms of scientific data and published insights, we nowadays have a good knowledge pool and best practices on how to assess impact beyond the purely quantitative publication output. Building on previous experiences, we structure our evaluation and impact assessment along logic models and work with a mix of qualitative and quantitative data gathering instruments to follow-up on the project activities and the outcomes for different stakeholder groups. As we want to integrate the different views and interests of our stakeholders, we plan to make the whole evaluation process as participatory as possible.

As our case study cycles are all embedded in real world scenarios where stakeholders are interacting at local, national or even international level, the core evaluation team relies very much on the consortium partners leading case studies on engaging the case study actors and collecting data according to the above mentioned plan. We expect this participatory approach towards evaluation to be a rough and challenging journey that will however reward all actors with valuable insights into how the GREAT approach can contribute to more political and social engagement on current climate policy issues and to closing the gap between citizens and policymakers in alternative and beneficial ways for all people involved.

Our next step is to implement the process along the different case studies. As we do suggest a modular approach, we will consider the appropriate approach for each of the case studies in close collaboration with project partners and especially those leading a case study. We also plan some capacity building workshop for the next consortium meeting to make sure that evaluation instruments can be implemented by the partners who may work on cases studies at local or national level. We have already started testing some of the methods above during the first GREAT test cycle and will continue to pre-test each instrument internally before implanting it in any of the case studies. Equally important for the further implementation of the suggested evaluation process will be the establishment of an open, trusted, and reflective collaborative culture across the case study stakeholders as well as the consortium partners. Mutual learning across the case studies and capacity building across the project partners is going to play an important role in the coming project phases.

Finally, we would like to stress again that all data management related to evaluation and impact assessment is in accordance with our ethical guidelines and whenever any personal data is collected we will apply the appropriate ethical research methods, such as informed consent and FAIR data principles. Most of the data that we will collect is however completely anonymous and thus less sensitive in terms of data handling.

9 References

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10 Appendix A: Evaluation Instruments for Participant Evaluation

Don't forget informed consent!

10.1 Pre/post questionnaire for DIBL and Playmob players

In general, the same items and response options provided in the original scales should be used for the assessment.

10.1.1 Collection of measures for affective climate change engagement

Measure	Item	Original Response Scale	Source
Personal Risk Perception	How concerned are you about climate change?	(1 = Not concerned at all, 7 = Very concerned)	(van der Linden, 2015)
	In your judgment, how likely are you, sometime during your life, to experience serious threats to your health or overall well-being, as a result of climate change?	(1 = Very unlikely, 7 = Very likely)	
	How serious of a threat do you believe that climate change is, to you personally?	(1 = Not serious at all, 7 = Very Serious)	
	How often do you worry about the potentially negative consequences of climate change?	(1 = Very Rarely, 7 = Very Frequently)	
Global/Societal Risk Perception	In your judgment, how likely do you think it is that climate change will have very harmful, long-term impacts on our society?	(1 = Very unlikely, 7 = Very likely)	(Pew Research Center, 2015)
	How serious of a threat do you think that climate change is to the natural environment?	(1 = Not serious at all, 7 = Very Serious)	
	How serious would you rate current impacts of climate change around the world?	(1 = Not serious at all, 7 = Very Serious)	
	How serious would you estimate the impacts of climate change for the United Kingdom?	(1 = Not serious at all, 7 = Very Serious)	
Climate Change Concern Index	In your view, is global climate change a very serious problem, somewhat serious, not too serious or not a problem?	Very serious – somewhat serious – not	(Pew Research Center, 2015)

		too serious – not a problem – DK/refused	
	Do you think global climate change is harming people around the world now, will harm people in the next few years, will not harm people for many years or will never harm people?	Now – in the next few years – not for many years – never – climate change does not exist – DK/refused	
	How concerned are you, if at all, that global climate change will harm you personally at some point in your lifetime? Are you very concerned, somewhat concerned, not too concerned or not at all concerned?	Very concerned – somewhat concerned – not too concerned – not at all concerned – climate change does not exist – DK/refused	
Political trust	How strongly do you feel that these groups will act in the interests of society and the environment?" <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal government; • Companies involved in [...] projects; • Environmental organisations; • Media; • Researchers studying at publicly funded research institutes; • United Nations; • European Union 	0=do not trust at all; 3= trust completely	(Braun et al., 2018) in similar forms but with different response scales and mentioning trust in the question (Merk et al., 2015; Merk & Pönitzsch, 2017)
Political Trust	Trust government to take action on climate change		(Elrick-Barr et al., 2016)
Political Trust	Trust in Local Government's Preparedness to Address Climate Change Issues.	Not prepared at all; Not very prepared; Somewhat prepared; Very prepared	(Shao et al., 2017)
Political Trust	How much do you trust the following groups to do what is right in regards to the climate crisis? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local government (e.g. local elected officials) 	1 (never trust) to 7 (completely trust)	(Castiglione et al., 2022)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State government (e.g. Department of Transportation, State level Energy Commissions) Federal government (U.S Environmental Protection Agency, U.S. Department of Health & Human Services) 		As the original survey is US-based, the question needs to be adapted to the local context.
Social trust	How much do you trust each of the following groups of people:	On a scale of 1 to 5 (1 = cannot be trusted at all, 5 = can be trusted a lot, 88 = don't know, 99 = refused).	(OECD, 2017) Annex 1, examples of trust measures
	People in your family?		
	People in your neighbourhood?		
	People you work or go to school with?		
	Strangers?		
Social trust (trust in strangers)	In general, you can trust people.	Strongly agree; Somewhat agree; Somewhat disagree; Strongly disagree	(originally by Naef & Schupp, 2009; taken from OECD, 2017)
	Nowadays, you can't rely on anybody.	Strongly agree; Somewhat agree; Somewhat disagree; Strongly disagree	
	How much do you trust strangers you meet for the first time?	No trust at all; Little trust; Quite a bit of trust; A lot of trust	
	When dealing with strangers, it's better to be cautious before trusting them.	Strongly agree; Somewhat agree; Somewhat disagree; Strongly disagree	
Climate emotions (instruction)	Perhaps you have heard that the Earth is currently experiencing climate change. The aim of this questionnaire is to examine your feelings on this subject.		(Marczak et al., 2023)

	<p>Rate the extent to which the following statements apply to you. For each statement, select one answer on the scale from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”.</p> <p>This questionnaire is not intended to verify your knowledge, therefore there are no right or wrong answers. Choose the answer that best describes what you feel.</p>		
Climate emotions (climate anger dimension)	I feel angry that the political and economic system that we live in harms the climate.	1 Strongly disagree	
	I am outraged that politicians allowed climate change to come this far.	2 Somewhat disagree	
	I feel outraged at corporations that harm the climate.	3 Neither agree, nor disagree	
	I feel anger when I think of politicians who delay efforts to mitigate climate change.	4 Somewhat agree	
Climate emotions (climate contempt)	It annoys me to watch people succumb to climate hysteria.	5 Strongly agree	
	I am annoyed by the constant publicity around climate change.		
	I am bored of hearing about climate change.		
	I am surprised that people experience strong emotions in connection with climate change.		
Climate emotions (climate enthusiasm)	The increasing public engagement with climate change gives me hope.		
	I believe that there are emerging solutions that will allow us to stop climate change.		
	Concrete actions for the climate allow me to be optimistic about the future.		

	Social mobilization in the fight against climate change makes me feel that together we can achieve this goal.		
Climate emotions (climate powerlessness)	I feel confused about what I can do to reduce climate change.		
	I am overwhelmed by how many aspects of life would need to be changed to limit climate change.		
	As an individual, I feel powerless with little agency over what happens with the climate.		
	I feel helpless when I think of how difficult it is to live in a climate-friendly way.		
Climate emotions (climate guilt)	I have a guilty conscience about not doing enough to mitigate climate change.		
	It upsets me that I have a big negative impact on the climate.		
	I feel guilty that my lifestyle contributes to climate change.		
	I am angry at myself for not doing enough to limit my negative impact on the climate.		
Climate emotions (climate isolation)	I feel like one of the few people who actually understand what climate change entails.		
	I feel lonely because most of the people around me don't care about climate change as much as I do.		
	I feel lonely because it's difficult to talk about my climate change concerns with other people.		
	I feel alienated because society considers concern for climate change as something strange.		

Climate emotions (climate anxiety)	Thinking about climate change makes me fear for the future of our children.		
	I am overwhelmed by the awareness of the approaching climate disaster.		
	Everything seems uncertain because of climate change.		
	I fear how climate change will affect me and my loved ones.		
Climate emotions (climate sorrow)	The thought of so many species going extinct under the pressure of climate change fills me with sorrow.		
	The thought that the world I know is disappearing forever because of climate change makes me sad.		
	I feel sorry about the possibilities we are losing forever because of climate change.		
	I am sad that so many living creatures suffer because of climate change.		

10.1.2 Collection of measures for cognitive climate change engagement

Measure	Item	Original Response Scale	Source
Self-assessed climate change knowledge	How much do you feel you understand about the issue of global warming or climate change?	A great deal A moderate amount Only a little Nothing at all	(Hamilton, 2018)
Self-assessed climate change knowledge	How would you rate your level of knowledge about global climate change?	I know almost nothing about this topic. I know very little about this topic.	(Howansky et al., 2010)

		<p>I have a moderate level of knowledge about this topic.</p> <p>I know a lot about this topic.</p> <p>I am an expert on this topic.</p>	
	<p>I am confident about my knowledge of climate change.</p>	<p>Strongly disagree</p> <p>Somewhat disagree</p> <p>Neither agree nor disagree</p> <p>Somewhat agree</p> <p>Strongly agree</p>	
Climate change beliefs	<p>Reality Dimension:</p> <p>I believe that climate change is real.</p> <p>Climate change is NOT occurring. (r)</p> <p>I do NOT believe that climate change is real. (r)</p>	<p>‘strongly disagree’ (1) to ‘strongly agree’ (7)</p>	<p>These are only the reality dimension and the causes dimension of the “climate change perceptions” scale by (Van Valkengoed et al., 2021)</p>
	<p>Causes Dimension:</p> <p>Human activities are a major cause of climate change.</p> <p>Climate change is mostly caused by human activity.</p> <p>The main causes of climate change are human activities.</p>		
Climate change beliefs (short scale)	<p>Reality Dimension:</p> <p>I believe that climate change is real</p>	<p>‘strongly disagree’ (1) to ‘strongly agree’ (7)</p>	<p>These are only the reality dimension and the causes dimension of the “climate change perceptions” short scale by (Van</p>
	<p>Causes Dimension:</p>		

	The main causes of climate change are human activities		Valkengoed et al., 2021)
Collective efficacy for climate action	I feel confident about the capability of our society to address the climate crisis very well.	1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree)	(Castiglione et al., 2022)
	Our society is able to solve the climate crisis if we invest the necessary effort.		
	I feel confident that our society will be able to effectively manage unexpected troubles created by the climate crisis.		
	Our society is totally competent to solve issues surrounding the climate crisis.		
	Humans can't reduce global warming, even if it is happening. (R)		
	Humans could reduce global warming, but people aren't willing to change their behavior, so we're not going to (R)		
	Humans can reduce global warming, and we are going to do so successfully.		
Internal political self-efficacy	I feel that I could do as good of a job in public office as most other people.	Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neither Agree nor Disagree, Agree, Strongly Agree, and Don't Know.	
	I think I am as well-informed about politics and government as most people.		
	I don't often feel sure of myself when talking with other people about politics and government.		
	I feel that I have a pretty good understanding of the important political issues facing our country.		

		I consider myself well-qualified to participate in politics.		
		Sometimes politics and government seem so complicated that a person like me can't really understand what's going on.		
External political self-efficacy		There are many legal ways for citizens to successfully influence what the government does.		
		Under our form of government, the people have the final say about how the country is run, no matter who is in office.		
		If public officials are not interested in hearing what the people think, there is really no way to make them listen.		
		People like me don't have any say about what the government does.		
Political Self-Efficacy Short Scale		I am good at understanding and assessing important political issues. (internal)	5-point Likert scale	(Beierlein et al., 2014)
		I have the confidence to take active part in a discussion about political issues. (internal)		
		Politicians strive to keep in close touch with the people. (external)		
		Politicians care about what ordinary people think. (external)		
Political Self-Efficacy		How much would you say the political system in (country) allows people like you to have a say in what the government does? (external)	Not at all 1 Very little 2 Some 3 A lot 4 A great deal 5 (Refusal) 7	(European Social Survey, 2016) This has the very important advantage that translations in all EU languages already exist!

		(Don't know) 8	
	And how much would you say that the political system in [country] allows people like you to have an influence on politics? (external)	1; Not at all 2; Very little 3; Some 4; A lot 5; A great deal (Refusal) 7 (Don't know) 8	
	How able do you think you are to take an active role in a group involved with political issues? (internal)	Not at all able 1 A little able 2 Quite able 3 Very able 4 Completely able 5 (Refusal) 7 (Don't know) 8	
	And how confident are you in your own ability to participate in politics? (internal)	Not at all confident 1 A little confident 2 Quite confident 3 Very confident 4 Completely confident 5 (Refusal) 7 (Don't know) 8	
Self-efficacy regarding climate action	I, as an individual, can promote climate action	1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree)	(Castiglione et al., 2022)
	I can encourage others to promote climate action		

	I, personally, have the skills and resources to address climate change		
	My individual actions benefit the climate action		
	I, personally, have skills and capabilities (such as teaching, writing, organising, public speaking, arts and creative work, outreach, others...) that can help reduce the climate crisis		
	I, personally, have skills that can successfully contribute to the actions and campaigns of a climate organization		

10.1.3 Collection of measures for behavioural climate change engagement

Measure	Item	Original Response Scale	Source
Collective action intentions	How often, if at all, are you willing to engage in the following environmental activities and actions?	5-point scale from 0 (never) through 2 (sometimes) to 4 (frequently)	Participatory action dimension. Adapted from (Alisat & Riemer, 2015) – turned it from self-reported past behaviour into intentions
	Educating myself about environmental issues (e.g., through media, television, internet, blogs, etc.)		
	Participating in an educational event (e.g., workshop) related to the environment.		
	Talking with others about environmental issues (e.g., spouse, partner, parent(s), children, or friends).		
	Using online tools (e.g., YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, ...) to raise awareness about environmental issues.		

	<p>Becoming involved with an environmental group or political party (e.g., volunteer, summer job, etc.).</p> <p>Financially supporting an environmental cause.</p> <p>Consciously making time to be able to work on environmental issues (e.g., working part time to allow time for environmental pursuits, working in an environmental job, or choosing environmental activities over other leisure activities).</p> <p>Participating in a community event which focused on environmental awareness.</p> <p>Participating in nature conservation efforts (e.g., planting trees, restoration of waterways).</p> <p>Spending time working with a group/organization that deals with the connection of the environment to other societal issues such as justice or poverty.</p>		
Collective action intentions	<p>Participating in a demonstration regarding an environmental policy</p> <p>Organizing a demonstration regarding environmental issues</p> <p>Taking part in a strike</p> <p>Blocking roads while demonstrating for environmental issues</p>	6-point Likert response scales (1 = “strongly disagree” and 6 = “strongly agree”)	(Van Zomeren et al., 2019) Instruction would need to emphasise intentions
Collective action intentions	There are different ways of trying to improve things in [country] or help prevent things from going wrong.	Yes (1), No (2), Refusal (7), Don't know (8)	Adapted from (European Social Survey, 2018)

	In the future, are you willing to do any of the following?		Originally, these items capture self-reported past behaviour. I adapted it so that intentions are measured
	...contact a politician, government or local government official?		
	...work in a political party or action group?		
	...work in another organisation or association?		
	...wear or display a campaign badge/sticker?		
	...sign a petition?		
	...take part in a lawful public demonstration?		
	...boycott certain products?		
	...post or share anything about politics online, for example on blogs, via email or on social media such as Facebook or Twitter?		

10.1.4 Collection of sociodemographic questions

Questions about some sociodemographic characteristics are considered extra sensitive under GDPR and we suggest not asking them (e.g., political beliefs, religious beliefs). Asking about extremely detailed information can also be problematic under GDPR. Below we provide some sociodemographic questions that are more GDPR-compliant (adapt them to the context of your country).

Measure	Item	Response Scale
Age	Which age range do you belong to?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18-24 years • 25-34 years • 35-44 years • 45-54 years • 55-64 years

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 65+ years • Prefer not to say
Gender	How do you identify your gender?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Male • Female • Non-binary/Third gender • Prefer not to say
Education	What is your highest level of education completed?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High School or less • Bachelor's Degree • Master's Degree or higher • Prefer not to say
Employment status	What is your current employment status?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employed full-time • Employed part-time • Unemployed • Student • Retired • Prefer not to say
Household composition	How many people live in your household?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 person • 2 people • 3 people • 4+ people • Prefer not to say
Language	<p>What is your primary language?</p> <p>For students it might be interesting to ask: What is the primary language you speak at home?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English/German/Spanish/Greek/... • ... • ...

Internet usage	How often do you use the internet?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily • Several times a week • Occasionally • Rarely • Never • Prefer not to say
Smartphone usage	How often do you use a smartphone?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily • Several times a week • Occasionally • Rarely • Never • Prefer not to say

10.2 Debriefing guideline for DIBL participants

This guideline can be adapted based on the needs of the specific case study.

Construct/ Measure	Item/Question	Response Scale	Medium	Reference
Game engagement	I enjoyed playing the game.	Strongly disagree – disagree – somewhat disagree – somewhat agree – agree – strongly agree	Interactive survey tool	Adapted from (Nussbaum et al., 2016)
	I was bored playing the game.			
	I want to play the game again.			
	I think playing the game was a waste of time.			

Game engagement	[Facilitators shows results in interactive survey tool] What else would you like to share with us about your experience playing the game?	Open questions	Group discussion	Self-developed
Experience as Public Engagement Process (Inclusiveness dimension)	During discussions, everyone could contribute equally.	Strongly disagree – disagree – somewhat disagree – somewhat agree – agree – strongly agree	Mentimeter or Kahoot (possibly followed by discussion)	Adapted from or rather, inspired by (Schroeter et al., 2016). They provide almost no information about the actual questions they used.
	During the discussions arguments from all participants were equally heard, independent of their status, gender, or age.	Strongly disagree – disagree – somewhat disagree – somewhat agree – agree – strongly agree	Mentimeter or Kahoot (possibly followed by discussion)	
	The discussions allowed for exchanging diverging opinions.	Strongly disagree – disagree – somewhat disagree – somewhat agree – agree – strongly agree	Mentimeter or Kahoot (possibly followed by discussion)	
	[Facilitators shows results in interactive survey tool] What else do you want to mention about the discussions during the game?	Open question	Group discussion	
Experience as Public Engagement Process	Which new perspectives or ideas		Group discussion	Adapted from or rather, inspired by

(Information exchange and learning dimension)	did you learn about during the game?			(Schroeter et al., 2016). They provide almost no information about the actual questions they used.
	What were your expectations of participating in the game? Were these expectations met?		Group discussion	
	Do you have any other feedback about your participation?		Group discussion	

10.3 Focus group guideline for DIBL participants

The aim of this focus group guideline is to capture collective experiences of participants who have played the dilemma game, how they interpret these experiences in retrospective, and how it impacted their thoughts, feelings, and actions. In general, the specific research interest behind the focus group will vary depending on the case study, the topic of the dilemma, and the results of the game. Therefore, we provide a general guideline covering **different key topics**, which can be modified for the specific use-case. The design of the guideline follows the suggestions by Hennink (2007).

Elements	Questions	Moderator/interviewer instructions
Introduction and defining the setting	Example icebreaker question: “As an introduction, I would ask everyone to tell us their name, (possibly: pronouns), favourite food, and favourite hobby.”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome participants • Explain purpose of the focus group • Explain the code of conduct during the discussion • Start with an icebreaker question

<p>Opening up the discussion</p>	<p>In [insert month/date], you participated in a game to solve problems related to climate change.</p> <p>In general, how did you like playing the game?</p> <p>What was your favourite part of the experience?</p>	<p>For these questions, make sure that everyone in the group briefly explains their experience so that every participant feels connected to the topic and recalls their participation.</p>
<p>Key topic 1: Climate Change Engagement</p>	<p>Next, I'd like to discuss the topic "climate change" as part of the game.</p> <p>Affective dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did you perceive the topic of climate change addressed during the game? • How did playing the game affect your feelings about climate change? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which aspects of the game contributed to this effect? • After this experience of playing, how do you think you personally will be affected by climate change? • And how do you think will your country be affected by climate change? <p>Cognitive dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did playing the game affect your thoughts about climate change? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which aspects of the game contributed to this effect? • What did you learn about climate change from playing the game? • What did you learn about solutions and strategies for climate change? <p>Behavioural dimension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did playing the game affect your motivation to take action on climate change? 	<p>Partly, the questions were inspired by or adapted from (Nicholson-Cole, 2004) (Whitmarsh, 2005) (Hensel et al., 2023). Make sure to cite appropriately.</p> <p>This first key topic covers different aspects of affective, cognitive, and behavioural climate change engagement.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which aspects of the game contributed to this effect? ● Since playing the game, which action for climate change have you taken? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Why? ○ If not, why not? ○ What would support you in taking action? ● In your opinion, who is responsible for doing something about climate change? 	
<p>Key Topic 2: Political Engagement</p> <p>It might make more sense to use these questions when combining players from different DIBL sessions into one focus group.</p>	<p>DIBL as public engagement process:</p> <p>Next, I want to talk about how you experienced the collaboration and discussions during the game.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How easy or difficult was it to share your own opinions and views during the game? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What could have made it easier? ● As a group, how did you manage diverging opinions or views of other players? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What could have helped you in addressing disagreements? ● What could you learn from other players during the discussions? ● Which other things did you take away from the discussions during the game? <p>Political efficacy:</p> <p>An important part of the game was making decisions to influence political processes and results. Please think about how it was for you to be involved in making political decisions during the game.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● After playing the game, how do you feel about your influence on political 	

	<p>decisions in your place of living? (note for interviewer: you may include another word such as city, viillage, etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Why do you feel that way? ○ What would be necessary for you to have more influence on political decisions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● After playing the game, how do you feel about your influence on political decisions in your country? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Why do you feel that way? ○ What would be necessary for you to have more influence on political decisions? ● How did the game affect your motivation to actively participate in politics? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What could your participation look like? ○ Which parts of the game influenced your motivation? ○ What would increase your motivation? ○ And what factors would hinder your motivation? 	
Summarising and concluding the discussion	We are now at the end of the discussion. To conclude, I have one last question. Considering all the issues discussed today, which do you feel are the most important when it comes to ...?	

10.4 Open-ended post-questions for Playmob participants

Construct/Measure	Question	Sources
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Risk perception	Thank you for sharing your opinion and helping us to combat climate change. After this experience: How do you think you personally will be affected by climate change?	Self-developed
Political Trust	Thank you for sharing your opinion and helping us to combat climate change. After this experience: Who do you trust to take action against climate change? Why?	Self-developed
Political self-efficacy	Thank you for sharing your opinion and helping us to combat climate change. After this experience: What could you do to make a difference in climate politics? How would that make a difference?	Self-developed
Behavioural intentions	Thank you for sharing your opinion and helping us to combat climate change. After this experience: What are you willing to do to fight climate change? Why?	Self-developed
Influence on political decisions	Thank you for sharing your opinion and helping us to combat climate change. After this experience: Which impact will your democratic participation have on decisions in climate policy? Why?	Self-developed
Data Sprint Invitation	Are you interested in this topic and the results of this global survey? Then join us in an online data sprint , where we will analyse the results together and discuss what they mean. Please leave your email address below to receive an invitation from the GREAT project. [open field for email address]	Self-developed

10.5 Debriefing guideline for participatory activities

Group discussion setting

Construct/ Measure	Item/Question	Response Scale	Medium	Reference
Enjoyment of participation	How did you experience the event?	5 point scale: very positive – positive – somewhat positive – somewhat negative – negative – very negative	Mentimeter/Kahoot	
Enjoyment of participation	Which aspect did you like the most?	Open question	Mentimeter/Kahoot (e.g., Wordcloud)	
Enjoyment of participation	Which aspect did you like the least?	Open question	Mentimeter/Kahoot	
Perceived gains from participation	What could you take away from this event?	Open question	Mentimeter/Kahoot	
Improved knowledge and skills	<p>For climate change issue/dilemma workshop participants: What did you learn about climate change?</p> <p>For game design/development participants: What did you learn about game design?</p> <p>For data sprint participants:</p>	Open question	Group discussion	

	What did you learn about working with data?			
General feedback	Do you have any other feedback about the event?	Open question	Group discussion	

11 Appendix B: Evaluation of Domain Experts (Scientific Impact)

The semi-structured interview guideline for domain experts below is meant to assess GREAT’s scientific impact. The guideline can be adapted based on the domain of the expert (e.g., expert in climate change, expert in survey methodology).

Preparation: the interviewee needs to have some information about the GREAT project, its activities, and outputs. If the interviewee is not familiar with GREAT, the interview needs to be preceded by a presentation of GREAT – otherwise, the questions don’t make sense.

Logic model outcomes:

- Did GREAT contribute to an ongoing research agenda?
- Depending on expert:
 - Did GREAT contribute to a new survey methodology?
 - Could GREAT provide information and data on the climate crisis?
- Did GREAT raise awareness and contribute to reaching specific target groups?
- Did GREAT provide new knowledge on citizen science and its application?

Interview Dimension	Interview question
Interviewee Background	What is your professional background?
	How would you describe your main interests in your work?
GREAT’s contribution to an ongoing research agenda	First, we would like to hear your thoughts about GREAT’s research activities. In your opinion, which new insights could GREAT contribute to your area of expertise?
	What are the shortcomings of GREAT’s methods and approaches?
	What are the limitations of GREAT’s results?

	<p>Building on GREAT's results, what would be new research questions you would like to explore?</p>
<p><u>For survey/methodology experts:</u></p> <p>GREAT's contribution to a new survey methodology</p>	<p>GREAT used different kinds of game-based survey tools (Playmob and DIBL).</p> <p>First, let's talk about the quiz tool.</p> <p>In your opinion, what is the potential of the quiz tool?</p> <p>What are the shortcomings or limitations of the quiz tool?</p> <p>For which purposes would you use the quiz tool yourself?</p>
	<p>Now, let's talk about the dilemma game.</p> <p>In your opinion, what is the potential of the dilemma game?</p> <p>What are the shortcomings or limitations of the dilemma game?</p> <p>For which purposes would you use the dilemma game yourself?</p>
<p><u>For climate experts:</u></p> <p>GREAT's contribution to information and data on the climate crisis</p>	<p>Moving on to climate change and strategies against the climate crisis.</p> <p>How did GREAT contribute to addressing the climate crisis?</p>
	<p>In your opinion, what is the potential of (GREAT's) games in research on climate change?</p>

	<p>What is the potential of (GREAT's) games in developing climate change solutions?</p> <p>How could you use the methods and results provided by GREAT in your own work?</p>
GREAT's contribution to citizen science	<p>Next, I'd like to talk about the citizen science activities in GREAT, where we involved different stakeholders in our research activities.</p>
	<p>Please describe your experience with citizen science.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If experience: What can you take away from GREAT's approach to citizen science? • If no experience: What would you need to apply citizen science in your own work?
	<p>In your opinion, what is the potential of combining gaming tools and citizen science?</p>
GREAT's contribution to raising awareness and reaching different target groups	<p>How useful do you think games are for reaching different target groups?</p> <p>How useful do you think games are for raising awareness about important topics?</p>
Conclusion of the interview	<p>Finally, I'd like to ask you if there is anything else you would like to say?</p> <p>That was my last question. Thank you for your time.</p>

12 Appendix C: Evaluation of Policy Stakeholders (Societal Impact)

This semi-structured interview guideline forms the basis for assessing the societal impact of GREAT together with policy stakeholders.

Preparation: Firstly, the interviewee needs to have information on the GREAT project, its activities, and outputs. If the interviewee is not familiar with GREAT, the interview needs to be preceded by a presentation of GREAT – otherwise, the questions don’t make sense. Secondly, the interviewer needs to provide the policy recommendations developed by citizens throughout the GREAT activities (results of the DIBL games, participatory activities), as the final part of the interview will discuss these recommendations.

- GREAT method for citizen communication and engagement
- The potential of games for social change
- Discussion of citizens’ policy recommendations and perspectives on policy learning

Interview Dimension	Interview question
Interviewee Background	What is your professional background?
	How would you describe your main interests in your work?
<i>Presentation of citizens’ recommendations for the climate crisis</i>	
Opinions about citizens’ recommendations and policy learning (three questions on policy learning adapted from (Huitema et al., 2010))	In general, what do you think about these recommendations?
	Which new knowledge or facts did you learn from these recommendations?
	Which new insights or considerations about this topic did you develop based on the recommendations?

	How did your view of citizens [or any involved social group] change now that you know about their recommendations?
The GREAT method of using games for communication, participation, and engagement	<p>Now, I'd like to talk about your opinion on the game-based tools we have developed in GREAT.</p> <p>In your opinion, what is the potential of the quiz tool ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... for communicating with citizens? • ... for gathering opinions on current issues from different target groups? • ... for facilitating political participation?
	<p>In your opinion, what is the potential of the dilemma game ...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ... for communicating with citizens? • ... for gathering opinions on current issues from different target groups? • ... for facilitating political participation?
The potential of games for social change	In your opinion, what is the potential of digital games to change awareness, or practices?
	Which elements of digital games could contribute to this change?
	What are the limitations of using digital games for (social) change?
	How could the experiences players make in a game influence actions in their everyday life?

	<p>Consider the challenges you face in your work. How could games help to address these challenges?</p>
<p>Conclusion of the interview</p>	<p>Finally, I'd like to ask you if there is anything else you would like to say?</p> <p>That was my last question. Thank you for your time.</p>

